

Diagnostic Accuracy of Tympanogram in Children with Otitis Media with Effusion Taking Myringotomy Findings as Gold Standard

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Abstract

Objective: Tympanometry is a non-invasive tool for preoperative assessment of otitis media with effusion. While myringotomy serves a therapeutic role, its diagnostic value is equally critical in confirming otitis media with effusion (OME). This study aims to determine the diagnostic accuracy of tympanogram in pediatric patient with suspected OME taking myringotomy findings as gold standard.

Methodology: A descriptive study was conducted in the Department of ENT, Jinnah Hospital Lahore during July 2024 and January 2025. Non probability, purposive sampling was used. A total of 122 pediatric patients of both genders, aged between 3-12 years, who underwent tympanometry followed by myringotomy, were included in this study. Each patient underwent tympanometric assessment followed by myringotomy with a radial incision in anteroinferior quadrant of tympanic membrane.

The operative findings observed during the myringotomy procedure were carefully documented.

Results: Sample included 88(72.1%) males and 34(27.9%) females with mean age of 7.77 ± 3.43 years. The sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, negative predictive value, and diagnostic accuracy of tympanometry for diagnosis of OME taking myringotomy as the gold standard was 98.0%, 81.8%, 96.1%, 90.0% and 95.1%, respectively.

Conclusion: Study concluded that diagnostic accuracy of tympanogram was comparable with myringotomy among pediatric patients with otitis media with effusion.

INTRODUCTION

The otitis media with effusion which also called glue ear, secretory or serous otitis media is described as the emergence of non-purulent fluid within middle ear without any symptoms associated with acute otitis media generally for greater than ninety days with intact ear drum.^[1] OME ranks as the most common disease affecting children. As the leading cause of acquired hearing loss in childhood, OME often develops early in life.^[2-5] It is considered a major cause for hearing impairment among almost 42 million individuals worldwide while the OME prevalence differs between 1.3 to 31.3 percent globally. Several studies carried out in Pakistan reported that OME prevalence is between 6.92% to 11.5%.^[6] About 80 percent of children have experienced OME at the age of four years, however, a decline is observed in the prevalence of OME beyond six years of age for these children.^[7] While most of the episodes resolve impulsively within three months, almost 25 percent of the cases persist for three months or more, classified as persistent OME.^[8] If the hearing loss remains persistent or reemerges frequently, it could badly affect the development of children, behavior as well as achievement at school. Furthermore, the children who have OME longer duration most commonly face problems with behavior as well as cognitive sequelae in their later life.^[9]

The accurate identification of OME is significant to make sure the fast intervention.^[10] Several techniques other than the otoscopy have been suggested for the diagnosis of OME to enhance the diagnostic accuracy, including pneumatic otoscopy, micro-otoscopy, tympanometry

and myringotomy.^[11] The myringotomy is believed as gold standard to ascertain the absence / presence of OME. As the myringotomy is one of the invasive procedures that needs general anesthesia, thus due to ethical consideration it is not carried out among asymptomatic children.^[12] Tympanometry is an objective, non-invasive, painless test and does not rely on patients' responses.^[13] It is gaining acceptance as an objective measure of assessing middle ear inflammation; however, the tympanometry accuracy in OME diagnosis, particularly among cases confirmed with myringotomy, continues to be of great interest. The tympanometry is a technique that measure the compliance of tympanic membrane as well as middle ear system through modifications in the air pressure within ear external canal.^[10] The tympanometry offers graphical display regarding middle-ear function. The tympanograms obtained through tympanometry are categorized as Type-A (normal, peaked), Type-B (abnormal, flat) and Type-C (middle-ear negative pressure, probable pathology). Type-B tympanogram classically identifies either the middle-ear effusion (ear canal low volume) or the perforation (ear canal high volume). Most significant cause for middle-ear effusion, and therefore the type-B tympanograms, is OME. Although, the Type-B tympanograms could also be noticed during less common circumstances such as tympanosclerosis or middle-ear tumors. In spite of widespread usage in the clinical settings, the evidence regarding tympanometry diagnostic accuracy differs across the studies. For the identification of OME among pediatric patients, tympanometry has 90 to 94 percent sensitivity, but the specificity is observed between 50 to 75 percent when compared to myringotomy which is the gold standard.^[14]

Comparing the tympanometric findings with myringotomy results offers an unflinching assessment regarding diagnostic accuracy. In Pakistan, very few studies have been carried out that compared the myringotomy and tympanometry in the pediatric OME, causing a lack of region-specific data to guide the clinical decision-making. Thus, current study aims to assess the diagnostic accuracy of tympanometry against myringotomy findings among children with suspected OME. The results of this research are expected to strengthen the local evidence,

promote cost-effective diagnosis, and support early management strategies to decrease the burden of preventable hearing loss among children in Pakistan.

METHODOLOGY

A descriptive study was conducted in the Department of ENT, Jinnah Hospital Lahore from July 2024 to January 2025.

During study 122 patients were enrolled for tympanometry and myringotomy due to otitis media with effusion symptoms. Sample size was calculated by using 85.7% sensitivity, 86.3% specificity, 85.9% prevalence of disease (diagnostic accuracy) of tympanometry for the diagnosis of OME taking myringotomy as gold standard with 1.75% precision, 95% confidence level and 10.0% expected dropout rate (Mehdi et al., 2023).

Sensitivity/Specificity - Estimation

Expected sensitivity:	<input type="text" value="85.7"/>
Expected specificity:	<input type="text" value="86.3"/>
Prevalence of disease (p):	<input type="text" value="85.9"/>
Precision (\pm expected):	<input type="text" value="1.75"/>
Confidence level $100(1 - \alpha)$:	<input type="text" value="95"/> %
Expected dropout rate:	<input type="text" value="10"/> %
<input type="button" value="Calculate"/> <input type="button" value="Reset"/>	
Sample size for sensitivity, n_{sen} =	<input type="text" value="-105"/>
Sample size for specificity, n_{spec} =	<input type="text" value="109"/>
Final sample size (largest), n =	<input type="text" value="109"/>
Final sample size (with 10% dropout), n_{drop} =	<input type="text" value="122"/>

Non probability, purposive sampling was used. Patients aged between 3 to 12 years with conductive hearing loss and air-bone gap >30 dB were included while patients with AOM, prior ear surgery, craniofacial anomalies such as Down syndrome and cleft palate were excluded from study.

Detailed history was obtained from parents regarding age, gender, duration of disease, OME on myringotomy and OME on tympanogram. Tympanometric assessments were carried out

with Interacoustics AT235h middle ear analyzer, as per Jerger's classification (Type A, B or C).^[10] Tympanometry was used to assess auditory function, with a probe tone at 226Hz. Normal ear canal volume ranged from 0.3 to 1mL. A flat Type-B tympanogram indicated fluid in middle ear of children. By following strict procedures, the study gathered reliable data on middle ear effusion, enhancing our understanding of pediatric auditory health conditions.

Following a precise radial incision in anteroinferior quadrant of tympanic membrane under general anesthesia, a myringotomy was performed to create a pain-free and controlled environment for the patient. Operative findings were carefully recorded for analysis, affirming the fluid presence in pediatric middle ear cavities.

The data was collected through proforma which was entered in computer software SPSS version 25.0. The data was analyzed with same software. The mean and standard deviation were computed for quantitative variables such as age and disease duration. Frequencies and percentages were determined for categorical variables including genders, OME as indicated on tympanograms, and instances of myringotomy. The metrics of sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), negative predictive value (NPV), and diagnostic accuracy were derived utilizing 2x2 contingency tables. Furthermore, post-stratification sensitivity and specificity concerning genders, age, and duration of disease were analyzed through 2x2 tables to observe potential effect modifications.

RESULTS

Sample comprised mostly 88 (72.1%) males with a mean age of 7.77 ± 3.43 years. Among these children, 77 (63.1%) had duration of disease more than 10 days and the mean duration was 13.5 ± 1.2 days. All patients underwent tympanogram and myringotomy. The OME was found positive among 100 (82.0%) patients on myringotomy while it was positive among 102 (83.6%) patients on tympanogram (Table-1).

The diagnostic performance of tympanometry in detecting OME was evaluated using myringotomy as the reference standard. The sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV),

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negative predictive value (NPV), and overall diagnostic accuracy of tympanometry was 98.0%, 81.8%, 96.1%, 90.0%, and 95.1%, respectively (Table-2).

Stratified analysis based on genders, age groups, and duration of illness revealed consistently high sensitivity and specificity of tympanometry in the identification of OME (Table-3,4,5).

Table-1: Frequency distribution of different variables (n=122)

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Male	88	72.1
Female	34	27.9
Age groups		
3-7 years	48	39.3
8-12 years	74	60.7
Duration of disease		
≤10 days	45	36.9
> 10 days	77	63.1
OME on myringotomy		
Positive	100	82.0
Negative	22	18.0
OME on tympanogram		
Positive	102	83.6
Negative	20	16.4

Table-2: Detection of OME on myringotomy vs. tympanogram

OME on tympanogram	OME on myringotomy		Total
	Positive	Negative	

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Positive	98	4	102	Sn=98.0%
Negative	2	18	20	Sp=81.8%
Total	100	22	122	PPV=96.1% NPV=90.0% DA=95.1%

Sn=sensitivity, Sp=specificity, PPV=positive predictive value,

NPV=negative predictive value,

DA=diagnostic accuracy

Table-3: Stratification of detection of OME on myringotomy vs tympanogram with respect to genders

Gender	OME on tympanogram	OME on myringotomy		Total	
		Positive	Negative		
Male	Positive	68	4	72	Sn=97.1%
	Negative	2	14	16	Sp=77.8%
	Total	70	18	88	PPV=94.5% NPV=87.5% DA=93.2%
Female	Positive	30	0	30	Sn=100.0%
	Negative	0	4	4	Sp=100.0%
	Total	30	4	34	PPV=100.0% NPV=100.0% DA=100.0%

Sn=sensitivity, Sp=specificity, PPV=positive predictive value,

NPV=negative predictive value,

DA=diagnostic accuracy

Table-4: Stratification of detection of OME on myringotomy vs. tympanogram with respect to age groups

Age groups	OME on tympanogram	OME on myringotomy		Total	
		Positive	Negative		
3-7 years	Positive	35	3	38	Sn=81.4%
	Negative	8	2	10	Sp=40.0%
	Total	43	5	48	PPV=92.1% NPV=20.0% DA=77.1%
8-12 years	Positive	56	8	64	Sn=98.3%
	Negative	1	9	10	Sp=52.9%
	Total	57	17	74	PPV=87.5% NPV=90.0% DA=87.8%

Sn=sensitivity, Sp=specificity, PPV=positive predictive value,

NPV=negative predictive value,

DA=diagnostic accuracy

Table-5: Stratification of detection of OME on myringotomy vs. tympanogram with respect to duration of disease

Duration of disease	OME on tympanogram	OME on myringotomy		Total	
		Positive	Negative		
≤10 days	Positive	36	1	37	Sn=97.3%
	Negative	1	7	8	Sp=87.5% PPV=97.3%

	Total	37	8	45	NPV=87.5% DA=95.6%
> 10 days	Positive	62	3	65	Sn=98.4% Sp=78.6%
	Negative	1	11	12	PPV=95.4%
	Total	63	14	77	NPV=91.7% DA=94.8%

Sn=sensitivity, Sp=specificity, PPV=positive predictive value, NPV=negative predictive value,

DA=diagnostic accuracy

DISCUSSION

Otitis media with effusion is a common cause for hearing issues among children, affecting their development. This condition can cause speech delays, behavioral problems, and academic struggles, particularly when it occurs early. Early and accurate diagnosis using techniques like tympanometry is crucial to prevent long-term negative impacts on a child's growth and education.^[4] Therefore, current study was carried out to assess the diagnostic accuracy of tympanogram versus gold standard myringotomy findings among children with otitis media with effusion. The findings of our study showed that majority (72.1%) of the patients were males and only 27.9% were females. A similar study carried out by Mehdi and teammates (2023) showed almost comparable results who reported that 64.2% patients were males and 35.8% patients were females.^[11] The results of a study done by Oleiwi and Naser (2022) highlighted that more than half (57.5%) of patients were males and 42.5% were females.^[15] Iftikhar and Aslam (2023) confirmed in their study that 50.7% patients were males and 49.3% were females.^[16]

It was found during study that 39.3% patients were 3 to 7 years old and 60.7% were 8 to 12 years old while the mean age was 7.77 ± 3.43 years. But a study conducted by Mehdi and teammates (2023) indicated that 51.2% patients were 3 to 7 years old, 48.8% were 8-12 years old

and the mean age was 7.35 ± 2.41 years.^[11] Another study performed by Oleiwi and Naser (2022) elucidated that 56.3% patients were 5 to 7 years old and 43.7% were 8-12 years old.^[15]

As far as duration of disease is concerned, study disclosed that only 36.9% patients had duration of disease up to 10 days while majority (63.1%) had duration of disease more than 10 days. The mean disease duration was 13.5 ± 1.2 days. But a study undertaken by Mehdi and teammates (2023) exhibited better scenario and reported that more than half (56.7%) patients had duration of disease up to five days and 43.3% had more than five days and mean duration of disease was 4.97 ± 2.04 days.^[11]

During study all patients experienced myringotomy and tympanogram to assess the effectiveness of both methods, study indicated that on myringotomy, which is the gold standard, the OME was found positive among 82.0% patients while on tympanogram the OME was found positive among 83.6% patients. A study conducted by Oleiwi and Naser (2022) demonstrated that on myringotomy the OME was found positive among 71.2% patients while on tympanogram the OME was found positive among 77.5% patients.^[15]

The results of our study revealed that sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV and overall DA of tympanometry taking myringotomy as gold standard was 98.0%, 81.8%, 96.1%, 90.0%, and 95.1%, respectively, which showed that tympanometry also has good sensitivity for OME. A study carried out by Mehdi and teammates (2023) reported that sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV and DA of tympanometry for the diagnosis of OME taking myringotomy as gold standard was 85.7%, 86.3%, 89.4%, 81.7% and 85.9%, respectively.^[11] In their study Anwar and fellows (2016) demonstrated that sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV and DA of tympanometry was 85.85%, 72.22%, 94.44%, 48.14% and 83.76%, respectively.^[17] A most recent study undertaken by Arif and comrades (2025) reported that sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV and DA of tympanometry in investigating OME was 92.5%, 85.7%, 89.2%, 90.1% and 88.8%, respectively.^[10] Eyigör and companions (2015) indicated in their study that sensitivity, specificity, PPV and NPV of tympanometry was 93.6%, 21.3%, 73.9% and 58.1%, respectively.^[18] Results of a study carried out by Muderris and colleagues (2013)

highlighted that tympanometry sensitivity was 84.48%, specificity was 84.62%, PPV was 88.56% and NPV was 89.2%.^[19] A study performed by Khmmas and coworkers (2016) elucidated that sensitivity and specificity of tympanogram were 89% and 63% while the accuracy was 83%.^[20] Lee and Yeo (2004) reported in their study that sensitivity was 87.5% and the specificity was 0.0%.^[21]

Our study further highlighted that sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV and overall DA of tympanometry taking myringotomy as gold standard among male patients was 97.1%, 77.8%, 94.5%, 87.5%, and 93.2%, respectively, while among female patients was 100.0% for sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV and overall DA. Likewise, sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV and overall DA of tympanometry taking myringotomy as gold standard among patients age group 3-7 years was 81.4%, 40.0%, 92.1%, 20.0% and 77.1% while among patients age group 8-12 years was 98.3%, 52.9%, 87.5%, 90.0% and 87.8%, respectively. A similar study undertaken by Arif and comrades (2025) indicated that sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV and overall DA of tympanometry taking myringotomy as gold standard among patients age group 2-5 years was 90.2%, 82.4%, 87.5%, 86.3%, 88.1% and among patients age group 6-8 years was 93.1%, 86.7%, 90.8%, 89.7%, 90.5% while among patients age group 9-12 years was 94.5%, 88.9%, 91.2%, 82.1%, 91.8%, respectively.^[10] A study done by Eyigör and companions (2015) reported that sensitivity, specificity, PPV and NPV of tympanometry taking myringotomy as gold standard among patients age group 1-2 years was 98.0%, 11.8%, 76.2%, 66.7% and among patients age group 3-4 years was 89.3%, 11.3%, 68.0%, 33.3% and among patients age group 5-6 years was 96.0%, 14.9%, 71.6%, 62.5% while among patients age group 7-17 years was 93.1%, 32.7%, 77.8%, 65.3%, respectively.^[18] The results of our study also demonstrated that sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV and overall DA of tympanometry taking myringotomy as gold standard among patients who had duration of disease <10 days was 97.3%, 87.5%, 97.3%, 87.5% and 95.6% while among patients who had duration of disease >10 days was 98.4%, 78.6%, 95.4%, 91.7% and 94.8%, respectively.

CONCLUSION

Present study assessed the diagnostic accuracy of tympanogram versus gold standard myringotomy findings: pediatric otitis media with effusion perspective. During study all patients experienced tympanogram and myringotomy. The findings of our study confirmed that 102 patients (83.6%) were found positive for OME on tympanogram while 100 patients (82.0%) were found positive for OME on myringotomy which is considered gold standard for the identification of otitis media with effusion. Study concluded that diagnostic accuracy of tympanogram was comparable with myringotomy among pediatric patients with otitis media with effusion. Further studies are needed on large scale to compare the diagnostic accuracy of tympanogram and myringotomy.

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